
LISTENING METHODOLOGIES FOR EFL STUDENTS TO IMPROVE LISTENING SKILLS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7803305>

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Abstract.

Understanding of English native's speech is not an easy going activity for each learner, when learning English as a second or foreign language, as the speaker talks fast and uses different accent, stress and abbreviations in their listening speech. As a result, students feel frustrated and anxious from not fully understanding the listening and may be lost easily. Moreover, listening is the skill which is used actively to comprehend while interacting in the language and doing activities related to this type of skill. The aim of this article is to give some listening strategies to help EFL/ESL learning students while doing listening activities.

Keywords.

listening techniques, EFL/ESL learning students, listening activities.

Introduction.

English is one of the languages that many countries learn as a second or foreign language in their country, however learning this language is not easy and to learn we need to develop several skills such as listening, writing, speaking, and reading skills. Listening is the skill that most students have difficulties and lose the speakers ideas and fail in the activities. While listening the speakers speak fast use different accent, abbreviated words and academic new lexic that students do not know and these causes many misunderstanding in the students mind. Students feel anxiety, stress, frustration and lose the motivation to learn the language and may stop learning the language. Therefore, knowing and using special strategies in listening many help students stay focused on the listening, understand the speakers ideas and improve their language skills.

Listening is the skill and defined as "the process through which spoken language is translated to meaning in the mind." [1]. When we listen to someones speech or statement our brain recieves information and the statement that we comprehend are the meaning and listening process goes in this way. But , when

listening to foreign language the brain doesn't understand all words and cause problems for listeners.

The range of topics that the student is interested in learning about and the language proficiency level must both be taken into consideration when selecting teaching materials. There will be a motivation to frequently attend classes in this situation. After all, learning a language ought to be enjoyable rather than a job. For the same reason, it is preferable to build lessons up gradually rather than starting out by, say, viewing a two-hour movie. Since it can be difficult to listen to a foreign language at first, you should be the first to include audio and video clips in your training.[2]

Main part.

To make it easier for you to comprehend the main ideas, use keywords or key phrases. You can infer that the speaker is talking about a business trip to New York from last year if you understand the words "New York," "business trip," and "last year." This might appear clear to you, but keep in mind that the speaker is still speaking. Imagine if a buddy of yours who speaks English tells you, "I got this fantastic tuner from JR's. I can now listen to broadcasts on National Public Radio because it was so inexpensive." If you concentrate on the word "tuner," you can get frustrated since you don't know what it means. You will likely start to understand if you think contextually. For instance, the past tense of buy is bought, listening is simple, and radio is evident. Now that you know: In order to listen to the radio, he purchased a tuner. A radio must be some sort of tuner. Here is a straightforward illustration, but it shows what you should pay attention to: Instead of the terms you don't understand, focus on the ones you do. [3]

Another strategy may be using pre-, while- and post- listening activities to improve the comprehension of listening. In addition, productive and distinctive listening methods in modern pedagogy include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening skills are best learned through simple, engaging activities that focus on the learning process rather than the end result. ESL and EFL educators are therefore expected to create lessons with them, and it has been decided to introduce several methods.

1. Mock interview. It is seen as an effective and non-threatening way for students to develop stronger skills through interpersonal activities. In this instruction, assign the student to her two or three her small groups and give her specific listening tasks to perform. For example, a teacher may interview one student with another for a position in a company or an article in a newspaper.

2. Reliability. "Authentic listening materials are print, video, and audio materials that students encounter in their daily lives, such as address change forms, job applications, menus, voicemail messages, radio programs, and videos. It wasn't created specifically for classroom use, but it's a great learning tool for students just because it's authentic." [4]

Interpersonal activities like mock interviews and storytelling are a safe and effective technique for kids to improve their listening abilities. A particular listening exercise places the students in small groups of two or three to complete. Through a useful technique for teaching listening skills to pupils, large group activities also provide an opportunity for the student to contribute. You might perhaps start with a basic activity for the group. The first task requires students to form groups of five or more and learn about the interests or pastimes of at least two other group members. Encourage students to ask clarifying questions throughout the task, and you may let them take notes if it would be beneficial. You can coach children in listening skills by playing audio clips from radio shows, lectures, podcasts, and other audio messages. Video clips, such as short sketches, documentary films, dramatic or comic content, news shows, and interview pieces, are the second best tool for teaching listening skills. In a video segment, you can choose the duration and portion of the video based on the proficiency of your pupils, just like you can in an audio segment. [5].

These strategies are provided by scholars and they tested these strategies before suggesting them, as in my point of view, all these activities and strategies are used to improve the listening in the second stage. The initial thing is the willingness to study and having the strong wish to acquire the language fast, also self-motivation and inspiration, dedication are the key activities in the language learning activities. nevertheless, the role of teachers, parents and society also has a big influence on learning process. As the correct motivation by the society, proper motivation and support can help students in their lifetime.

The correct daily routine is also important, as if you use the day and rearrange daily routine in the correct way you can achieve needed results. Utilize of time and appreciation of it can be another key in language learning and in learning process.

IV. Conclusion.

To sum up the article, listening strategies are the keys to learn the language. Many strategies were provided to support the students, additionally teachers, parents, friends and society can help the learners in this way. Initially students

willingness to study appreciation of time and all other resources can be used in learning process.

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